

-6.4D. The extrapolation of linear relationship to wake
 $\rightarrow$
 phenols shows that $\Delta\mu=0$ as $p_k \rightarrow 7.3$. It estimates that the maximum value of $(\Delta' - \Delta)$ due to conjugation effect in weak H-bonded complexes i.e., the delocalization of the π -electrons through a hydrogen bond^{1a} is 2.00 D. The correction factor Δ , in fact measures the changes in the nature of polarity of the structure. Thus the possible conformers of molecules involved in complexes may be one of the factors to which Δ may depend upon. However the actual mechanism of its variation is still questionable.

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Synthesis of Naphtho α - and γ -Pyrone Derivatives from 1,4-Dihydroxy Naphthalene

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IN continuation of previous work¹ we have now studied the synthesis of α - and γ -pyrone derivatives from 1,4-dihydroxy naphthalene.

1,4-Dihydroxy naphthalene on condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of conc. sulphuric

acid gave 4-hydroxy-4'-methyl naphtho (1,2:6',5') α -pyrone (I, R=H) (m.p. 282°), earlier prepared by Desai and Sethna² by persulphate oxidation of naphtho (1,2:6',5') α -pyrone. Buu Hoi and Lavit³ who carried out this condensation in alcoholic solution using hydrogen chloride gas as the condensing agent obtained a product m. p. 206° to which they assigned the above structure. In order to ascertain the nature of this product we repeated Buu Hoi's work and obtained the product m.p. 206°. Its NMR spectrum showed the absence of a free hydroxyl group, but the presence of a 4-ethoxy group. On de-ethylation with anhydrous aluminium chloride it gave the product m.p. 282°, which when subjected to the action of hydrogen chloride in presence of alcohol gave back the product m.p. 206°. Buu Hoi's product is therefore 4-ethoxy-4'-methyl naphtho (1,2:6',5') α -pyrone (I, R=C₂H₅).

The γ -pyrone derivative was obtained from 1,4-dihydroxy naphthalene by refluxing it with ethyl acetoacetate in boiling diphenyl ether. It was different from the α -pyrone (I, R=H) and gave on alkaline hydrolysis 1,4-dihydroxy-2-acetyl naphthalene. It has been assigned 4-hydroxy-2'-methyl naphtho (1,2:6',5') γ -pyrone (II) structure. It is known that such a condensation gives γ -pyrone derivatives⁴.

Experimental

4-Hydroxy-4'-methyl naphtho (1,2:6',5') α -pyrone : A mixture of 1,4-dihydroxy naphthalene (2 g.), ethyl acetoacetate (4 ml.) and conc. sulphuric acid (8 ml.) was kept overnight. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture on crushed ice was soluble in alkali. It was crystallised from acetic acid. M.P. 282°. Yield 0.6 g. Desai and Sethna² reported m.p. 285°. IR (nujol) cm^{-1} : 3170 (OH), 1675 (CO).

The acetyl derivative : The above product (1 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and sodium acetate (1.5 g.) for 1.1/2 hr. and the product obtained crystallised from ethyl acetate in fine needles m.p. 183°. (Found : C, 71.37; H, 4.00. C₁₆H₁₂O₄ requires C, 71.64; H, 4.47%).

4-Ethoxy-4'-methyl naphtho (1,2:6',5') α -pyrone : A cooled solution of 1,4-dihydroxy naphthalene (2 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (4 ml.) in ethanol (25 ml.) was saturated with hydrogen chloride gas. The reaction

mixture was left for 6 hr. The solid obtained crystallised from acetic acid. The compound was found to be insoluble in dilute alkali and did not give an acetoxy derivative. M.p. 206°. (Found : C, 75.25 ; H, 5.39. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.56 ; H, 5.51%). IR (nujol) cm^{-1} : 1730 (CO). NMR ($CDCl_3$) (ppm) : 8.3–8.1 (2H, m, due to H-5 and H-8), 7.72–7.52 (2H, m, due to H-6 and H-7), 6.7 (1H, s, due to H-3), 6.3 (1H, s, due to H-3'), 4.22 (2H, q, due to OCH_2CH_3), 2.46 (3H, s, due to $-CH_3-4'$) and 1.6 (3H, t, due to $-OCH_2CH_3$).

The de-ethylation of this product with anhydrous aluminium chloride in benzene gave a product, whose m.p. and mixed m.p. with 4-hydroxy-4'-methyl naphtho (1,2 : 6',5') α -pyrone was 286°. On ethylation with diethyl sulphate in dry acetone and anhydrous potassium carbonate it gave Buu Hoi's product m.p. 206°.

4-Hydroxy-2'-methyl naphtho (1,2 : 6',5') γ -pyrone :

A mixture of 1,4-dihydroxy naphthalene (1.5 g.) in diphenyl ether (12 ml.) and ethyl acetoacetate (4g.) was refluxed for 2.1/2 hr. Petroleum ether was added to the reaction mixture after cooling. The solid obtained was soluble in dilute alkali. It crystallised from dimethyl formamide in tiny needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 315°. (Found : C, 74.04 ; H, 4.03. $C_{14}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 74.33 ; H, 4.42%).

1,4-Dihydroxy-2-acetyl naphthalene : The above γ -pyrone derivative (0.5 g) was refluxed with sodium hydroxide (20 ml. ; 20%) for 30 minutes. The mixture was cooled, diluted and acidified. The separated product crystallised from benzene, m. p. 215°. Mixed m. p. with 1,4-dihydroxy-2-acetyl naphthalene prepared as follows was not depressed.

1,4-Dihydroxy naphthalene was acetylated as usual and the mixture of 1,4-diacetoxy naphthalene (2 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (6 g.) was heated at 140° for 3 hr. On working as usual the product crystallised from benzene. It gave wine red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride and was soluble in alkali. It analysed for monoacetyl compound. M.P. 215°. Yield 0.5 g. (Found : C, 71.61 ; H, 4.73. $C_{12}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 71.29 ; 4.94%).

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Synthesis and Biological Activity of Some New N⁺ 3(2 phenyl quinazolin(3H)-4-one) Acyl Hydrazones

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SEVERAL new hydrazone derivatives have been synthesised by the condensation of 3(2-phenyl-quinazolin (3H)-4-one) acyl hydrazides with substituted aromatic aldehydes. All of these were screened for their antibacterial and insecticidal activities.

During recent years many workers have emphasized the bactericidal¹, herbicidal², insecticidal³ and fungicidal⁴ properties of various hydrazones. Several quinazolone derivatives have been shown to possess anticonvulsant^{5,6} and insecticidal⁷ properties. Keeping these important observations in view, some 3(2-phenyl quinazolin (3H)-4-one) acyl hydrazones have been synthesised to study their bactericidal and insecticidal properties.

I, X = OC_2H_5

II, X = $NHNH_2$

III, X = $NH-N=CHC_6H_4R$

The structure of the compounds were supported by elemental analysis, melting points, t.l.c. and infrared spectroscopy.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer which tally with those in literature.

The key intermediates I and II were prepared by the esterification of 3-(2-phenylquinazolin (3H)-4-one) alkanolic acid (which were prepared by the interaction of benzoxazinone with different amino acids) and then treatment with hydrazine hydrate respectively⁸.